

Evaluation of Students Admission Program at Indonesia Defense University

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ABSTRACT: *University as a form of higher education aims to form quality human resources to face challenges in the era of globalization. Student admissions is carried out to see whether the prospective student meets the quality standards set by a university. This is done so that students who are accepted are individuals who have good quality standards because later these students will have responsibility for the development of the college. Thus, many universities conduct strict selection of these prospective students. One of the state universities that conducts strict selection in the admission of prospective students is the Indonesia Defense University. The initial problem found in the student admission process was the lack of institutions that would accept Indonesia Defense University alumni and many students are placed in the wrong majors throughout their admission. This study will analyze the evaluation of students admission program at Indonesia Defense University using qualitative method and CIPP Model. The results of this study show that based on the evaluation using CIPP Model, Indonesia Defense University must change their strategies on students admission program to overcome the problems they are facing.*

KEYWORDS – *CIPP Model, evaluation, Indonesia Defense University, students admission, university.*

I. INTRODUCTION

University as a form of higher education aims to form quality human resources to face challenges in the era of globalization. To achieve this goal, a university carries out a student admission process which usually consists of several stages to see the criteria and abilities of prospective students. In the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture No. 6 of 2020 [1], student admission is carried out with the following principles: equitable, accountable, flexible, efficient, and transparent. Student admissions is carried out to see whether the prospective student meets the quality standards set by a university. This is done so that students who are accepted are individuals who have good quality standards because later these students will have responsibility for the development of the college. Thus, many universities conduct strict selection of these prospective students. One of the state universities that conducts strict selection in the admission of prospective students is the Indonesia Defense University.

The strict admission process carried out by the university is because Indonesia Defense University students will get full scholarships that are not available at other universities in Indonesia, specifically for the third diploma or vocational and undergraduate programs. In addition, the admission process is carried out to achieve the objectives of Indonesia Defense University as an organization, namely to carry out the development of Indonesia Defense University which is oriented to the Threefold Mission of Higher Education (*Tridharma Perguruan Tinggi*) to achieve national education standards and world class defense university. In addition, the Indonesia Defense University's goal to produce intellectual human resources and have the spirit of defense must be supported by optimal admission in accordance with the needs of Indonesia Defense University as an organization. The establishment of Indonesia Defense University is also one of the government's efforts to

provide an understanding to the public that defense and national security are the duties of all citizens according to their abilities, not only military tasks.

The initial problem found in the student admission process was the lack of institutions that would accept Indonesia Defense University alumni. This of course will have an impact on university accreditation. Other than that, for the past years the student admission program at Indonesia Defense University has experienced continual faculty and administrative turnover, resulting in changes in policies, practices, teaching, and advising. Students and teachers notice of these changes and vocalized their dissatisfaction with the lack of program evaluation, lack of consistent advising, and lack of leadership. The student admission program itself is a management process consisting of planning, organizing, mobilizing, and evaluating which is an integral part of achieving organizational goals. Evaluation is a measure of the success of programs that have been planned and carried out by Indonesia Defense University. Thus, it is important for the Indonesia Defense University to evaluate the admission process for prospective students so that Indonesia Defense University's goal as a world class defense university can be achieved. The evaluation model that will be used to evaluate Indonesia Defense University student admission process is the CIPP Model which consists of four evaluation components, namely Context, Input, Process, Product.

This paper will discuss an evaluation the student admission program to improve program quality and ultimately to increase both student and university satisfaction. Hence, the research question is: How was the evaluation of Indonesia Defense University students admissions recruitment program using the CIPP Model? The contribution of the paper is to make recommendation to the university itself so they can improve the quality of student and teachers of Indonesia Defense University to help the institutions achieve its goals. In addition, there has never been any research related to the evaluation of the new student admissions program conducted by Indonesia Defense University.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Evaluation is defined as the provision of information that can be used as consideration in decision making [2]. Evaluation is also defined as a process of evaluating something based on predetermined criteria or goals, which is continued with decision making on the object being evaluated [3]. According to Stufflebeam [4] the CIPP Model rests on the view that the most important goal of program evaluation is not to prove, but to improve. The CIPP Model is applied in order to support organizational development and help organizational leaders and staff to obtain and use input systematically so that they are better able to meet important needs or, at a minimum, to do their best with existing resources [5]. According to Stufflebeam, the CIPP Model has four continuous elements. First, evaluation of the context leads to the identification of organizational strengths and weaknesses and to providing input to improve the organization. Context evaluation also aims to assess whether the goals and priorities that have been set meet the needs of the parties to whom the organization is targeting. Second, the evaluation of inputs is intended to help determine the program to make the necessary changes. Input evaluation looks for constraints and potential available resources. Thus, input evaluation serves to help clients avoid wasted innovations that are expected to fail or waste resources.

Third, process evaluation basically checks the implementation of a predetermined. The aim is to provide input for managers or managers and their staff about the suitability between the implementation of plans and schedules that have been made previously and the efficient use of existing resources. If the plan needs to be modified or expanded, the process evaluation provides clues. Process evaluation can review the organization's plans and previous evaluations to identify important aspects of the organization that should be monitored. The main function of process evaluation is to provide input that can help organizational staff carry out programs according to plan, or perhaps modify plans that turn out to be bad. In turn, process evaluation becomes a vital source of information for interpreting product evaluation results. Fourth, product evaluation aims to measure, interpret, and assess program achievements. Product evaluation aims to assess the success of the program in meeting the needs of the program targets. These assessments of the success of the program or organization are collected from the people involved individually or collectively, and then analyzed.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

To satisfy the objectives of the research, qualitative research in a descriptive manner was held. This method offers a complete description and analysis of the research subject. Qualitative research is used to better understand every phenomenon that is not widely known and is used by researchers to describe things such as motivation, roles, values, attitudes and perceptions [6]. This study uses primary data obtained from observations and interviews and secondary data obtained from books, journals, and reports [7].

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on the data obtained, the admission process for prospective Indonesia Defense University students is divided into 4 (four) stages of selection. The first stage is the administrative selection, where prospective students must meet several administrative requirements to be able to proceed to the next selection stage. These requirements include having a high school diploma (for prospective undergraduate students in Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Biology with an average score of 9, while for diplomacy or vocational education the average value is 8.5 for the four subjects), an undergraduate diploma (for prospective master degree students with a minimum GPA of 3.00) and master degree diplomas (for prospective doctoral students with a minimum GPA of 3.5), physically and mentally healthy, not using illegal drugs, willing to sign a Student Contract Agreement, and so on. The second stage is TOEFL (Test of English as a Foreign Language) to see the ability of prospective students in mastering foreign language. Furthermore, prospective students who have passed the TOEFL threshold value set by Indonesia Defense University will carry out Academic Potential Test. This test is a psychological test that can reveal what an individual has achieved intellectually. The fourth stage in the admission process for prospective Indonesia Defense University students is interview. At this last stage, prospective students will be interviewed by Indonesia Defense University lecturers to see the perceptions of prospective students regarding defense issues.

The implementation of the educational process cannot be separated from the evaluation process. In producing a good quality education, evaluation is closely related to assessment. An evaluation must be carried out to see whether the program that has been implemented has been in accordance with the initial plan or not whether the program needs improvement or should it be maintained with various inputs from the evaluators. To evaluate the student admission program at Indonesia Defense University, CIPP Model will be used to answer some questions that could only be interpreted in relation to the core values. The first element is Context, whereas in the evaluation of student admission at Indonesia Defense University there are several things that must be considered such as what are the goals of the program and which goals are their priorities? To answer these questions, based on the data obtained, student admission at Indonesia Defense University has several goals to achieve, such as to create competent alumni in the field of state defense and national security and to make Indonesia Defense University as a world class defense university. These two goals are the priorities for Indonesia Defense University.

The next question which need to be asked is how well did the goals and priorities align with their needs, assets, opportunities, and problems? Indonesia Defense University itself has an opportunity that any other universities do not have, namely defense university. Indonesia Defense University also has a lot of assets like money and infrastructure supported by the government. Indonesia Defense University has assets and opportunities to help them to run their activities as well as their needs. But on the other hand, the problems which are faced by Indonesia Defense University is: only several people know this university and the lack of job opportunities so that alumni are not absorbed properly in the world of work. Indonesia Defense University believes that the student admission process held by the university has already been done properly. New students must pass several tests, from TOEFL, Academic Potential Test, interview, and so on. Based on this answer, Indonesia Defense University is faced with an option, whether they have to revise their goals and priorities or not. From context evaluation, the goals and priorities which have been set does not meet with the needs of Indonesia Defense University is targeting.

The second element is Input, whereas in the evaluation of student admission at Indonesia Defense University there are several things that must be considered such as will student admission program help the university achieve its goals and how does the student admission program align with its goals? To answer these questions,

we have to remember how the student admission program meet the stakeholders' needs. Indonesia Defense University has several majors concerning defense and national security. These majors are considered too rigid so some alumni cannot meet with the job's requirement because their majors are not aligned. So it can be conclude, that the students ability does not meet the stakeholders' needs. Other than that, on the process of student admission program, many prospective students are accepted but they are placed in the wrong majors. In other words, the majors they take are not linear with their previous majors so that students are not in the majors they want. This is happened because Indonesia Defense University wants to meet the admission quota. Based on the evaluation of inputs, it is stated that Indonesia Defense University must make necessary changes because the university itself faces constraints.

The third element is Process, whereas in the evaluation of student admission at Indonesia Defense University there are several things that must be considered such as how well student admission program seem to be moving Indonesia Defense University towards its goals? To answer this question, Indonesia Defense University must evaluate how effective their student admission program in meeting students' and stakeholders' needs. To evaluate this problem, Indonesia Defense University must change their strategies on student admission program so it can help them achieve their goals. The process of student admission consists of examining or testing the candidates before they are admitted to the university. As stated before, the problems faced is sometimes students are placed in the wrong majors. It is going to affect the university's accreditation itself later. It can be said that student admission program held by Indonesia Defense University sometimes do not meet the students' and stakeholders' needs because the teachings which has been done by the university sometimes do not meet the requirements in the world of work. Based on the evaluation of process, it can be concluded about the suitability between the implementation of plans and schedules that have been made previously and the efficient use of existing resources of Indonesia Defense University.

The last element is Product, whereas in the evaluation of student admission at Indonesia Defense University there are several things that must be considered such as how should the student admission program be modified to better meet their goals and how can they compensate for unforeseen outcomes? To answer these questions, it must be underlined that how student admission program at Indonesia Defense University be more effective in the future? Product evaluation aims to assess the success of the program in meeting the needs of the program targets. Indonesia Defense University has succeeded in creating qualified alumni, especially those who interested in defense and national security fields. But however, many people and institutions do not understand or interested in Indonesia Defense University alumni because they think it is too rigid and unapplicable. To overcome this problem, Indonesia Defense University must change their strategies, namely promoting Indonesia Defense University to people and institutions in Indonesia and make sure that the students are being placed in the right major, or at least according to their wishes and abilities so Indonesia Defense University will 'produce' more qualified alumni in the future.

V. CONCLUSION

The CIPP Model is relevant to student admission program at Indonesia Defense University in a variety of contexts. The model is flexible, comprehensive, and grounded in values that are co-created among student admission program. Broadening professional knowledge to encompass tools such as the CIPP Model will empower Indonesia Defense University to have a greater impact on the lives of their students, colleagues, and communities so that they can achieve their goals. Indonesia Defense University has opportunities and assets supported by the government to meet its needs and goals. CIPP Model help them to overcome the problems they are facing. Regarding the Concept element, Indonesia Defense University is faced with an option, whether they have to revise their goals and priorities or not. In the Input element, Indonesia Defense University majors are considered too rigid so some alumni cannot meet with the job's requirement because their majors are not aligned. So it can be conclude, that the students ability does not meet the stakeholders' needs. In the Process element, student admission program held by Indonesia Defense University sometimes do not meet the students' and stakeholders' needs because the teachings which has been done by the university sometimes do not meet the requirements in the world of work. Then there is must be something Indonesia Defense University do to overcome this problems. At last, in the Product element, Indonesia Defense University has succeeded in

creating qualified alumni, especially those who interested in defense and national security fields. But however, many people and institutions do not understand or interested in Indonesia Defense University alumni because they think it is too rigid and unapplicable. However, as the nature of CIPP is to involve stakeholders throughout the evaluation process, stakeholders who believe that the evaluation outcomes may not serve their own goals have ample opportunity to delay, obstruct, or derail the evaluation process. Arguably, however, resistance from stakeholders may also serve a purpose as may bring to light issues deserving of attention. So far, Indonesia Defense University does not consider changing their strategies to be their focus now. But, Indonesia Defense University must change their strategies to help them achieve its goals with the help of student admission program to create qualified alumni.

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